

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDY OF THE REACTION BETWEEN DICHROMATE AND HYDROGEN PEROXIDE. ACTION OF MANGANOUS SULPHATE

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Dichromate is quantitatively reduced by H_2O_2 to give chromic ions if the acid concentration is properly adjusted ($8N$ to $N/2-H_2SO_4$ or $2N$ to $N-HCl$). Four moles of H_2O_2 per mole of dichromate are required, which can be explained on the assumption that the dichromate (oxidation state Cr_2O_6) first acquires an unstable higher oxidation state, Cr_2O_{10} , from which oxygen is evolved and Cr_2O_3 (*i. e.*, chromic ions in acid solution) is left behind. When the acid concentrations are less, somewhat more than 4 moles of H_2O_2 are required, indicating either a higher oxidation state, Cr_2O_{11} , or self-decomposition of the peroxide. When manganous sulphate in excess is added before the peroxide is run in ($10N$ to $2N-H_2SO_4$), three moles of peroxide are required, perhaps in accordance with the mechanism, $Cr_2O_6 + 6MnO \rightarrow Cr_2O_3 + 3Mn_2O_3$; $3Mn_2O_3 + 3H_2O_2 \rightarrow 3Mn_2O_4 + 3H_2O$; $3Mn_2O_4 \rightarrow 6MnO + 3O_2$, so that the action of manganous ions is only catalytic.

A number of potentiometric methods of analysing hydrogen peroxide solution has been described, a critical review of which is given by Reichert *et al.* (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1939, 11, 194). It appears that a potentiometric method of estimation of H_2O_2 with $K_2Cr_2O_7$ has not yet been attempted.

When treated with hydrogen peroxide, acidic solutions of chromates produce the well-known blue perchromic acid (Sidgwick, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Oxford University Press, 1950, p. 1006), which quickly decomposes in aqueous solutions at ordinary temperatures, producing an equivalent amount of Cr^{3+} . The reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ by H_2O_2 is complicated by this fact, and there has been considerable controversy regarding the formation and composition of the blue perchromic acid. Carnot (*Compt. rend.*, 1888, 107, 948, 997, 107) found that the reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ by H_2O_2 was quantitative. Berthelot (*ibid.*, 1889, 108, 24, 157, 477) considered that due to the intermediate formation of unstable perchromic acids, the amount of H_2O_2 required to reduce the dichromate was likely to vary with the mode of admixture, the presence of particular acids, temperature and concentration. He found that very dilute dichromate in HCl required four moles of H_2O_2 per mole of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and represented the reaction as

He also found that dichromate in sulphuric acid required 3 moles H_2O_2 , when the latter was added to the former, but 5 moles, when the process was reversed. For 3 moles of H_2O_2 consumed per mole of dichromate, the reaction was set down as

For 5 moles, it was represented in two stages :

followed by

Cr_2O_7 was here assumed to be the anhydride of the intermediate perchromic acid, which he considered to be HCrO_4 .

According to Riesenfeld *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3380, 3578) only three moles of H_2O_2 per two moles of CrO_5 are required, irrespective of the mode of admixture. They considered that the reduction took place with the formation of an intermediate,

followed by

The results of Schwarz and Giese (*Ber.*, 1932, 66, 871) suggest that the anhydride of the intermediate perchromic acid is neither Cr_2O_7 nor Cr_2O_5 , but CrO_5 . This formula requires four moles of H_2O_2 per two moles of CrO_5 for the reduction, as is shown later.

Rai (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 193) assumes that the formation of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid may be due to the combination of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$ and Cr^{3+} , the latter generated by simultaneous reduction by H_2O_2 . The mechanism suggested by him would again require three moles of H_2O_2 per mole of dichromate reduced, the intermediate compound being $\text{Cr}_3(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$. Recent investigations by Glasner and Steinberg (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2559) indicate that the basic formula of the intermediate compound is CrO_5 . This agrees with the results of Schwarz and Giese (*loc. cit.*) and Evans (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4013) who find that the predominant equilibrium in an aqueous solution is

The formula CrO_5 for the blue perchromic acid requires four moles of H_2O_2 per two moles CrO_5 ,

This is followed by

A potentiometric titration of dichromate with H_2O_2 promised to be of much interest in this context and the present work was taken up with a view to obtaining a clearer picture of the reduction of dichromate by peroxide. The role of an excess of MnSO_4 , previously noted (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 721), has been further studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titration were all performed at room temperature ($24^\circ \pm 2^\circ$) using the potentiometric arrangements described earlier (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 313). The reaction mixtures, prepared as follows, were taken in the titration cell and kept stirred with a magnetic stirrer, half-molar peroxide being added from a burette: sulphuric acid mixtures (A) 8N, (B) 6N, (C) 4N, (D) 2N, (E) N, (F) N/2 and (G) N/10; hydrochloric acid mixtures (A) 2N, (B) N, (C) N/2 and (D) N/10. The concentration of dichromate was 0.005M in all these mixtures and 100 c.c. was taken for a titration.

Higher concentrations of HCl were avoided to eliminate the possibility of evolution of Cl_2 .

FIG. 1

A blackish precipitate appeared on addition of H_2O_2 , which soon redissolved, exhibiting a greenish tinge to the solution (orange due to dichromate). At the point

FIG. 2

of inflection, the colour changed over sharply from greenish yellow to blue, indicating complete reduction of Cr^{3+} . The black precipitate took long to dissolve when the

acid concentration was less than normal. The potentials were fairly steady after fifteen minutes of constant stirring. The potential drop at the equivalence point was 250-400 mv. The actual graphs are reproduced in Figs. 1 and 2 for sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid mixtures respectively, the letters corresponding to the individual mixtures. The inflection occurs at 4 moles of H_2O_2 in all H_2SO_4 mixtures except (G) where it is about 4.1. For HCl mixtures also, the H_2O_2 requirement is increased from 4 moles (A, B) to larger values when acid concentration is reduced (C=4.2, D=4.3).

To study the effect of an excess of $MnSO_4$, a series of mixtures, 0.005M- $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and 0.3M- $MnSO_4$, were prepared with decreasing H_2SO_4 concentrations: (A) 10N, (B) 8N, (C) 6N, (D) 4N, (E) 2N and (F) N. The corresponding graphs appear in Fig. 3.

On mixing the dichromate and manganous sulphate solutions, a deep cherry-red colour appeared, indicating oxidation of Mn^{2+} to Mn^{3+} . To complete the oxidation, the reaction mixture was stored in the dark for several hours before the H_2O_2 was run in. The depth of the red colour decreased as the peroxide was added, and the colour changed over to greenish blue at the equivalence point (not sharp). Ten minutes of stirring was necessary for a steady potential, and the potential drop at the equivalence point was about 400 mv. The peroxide requirement per mole of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was three in A to E, but higher when acid concentration was below 2N (3.5 moles H_2O_2 in F).

DISCUSSION

An understanding of the reactions taking place is simplified if we ignore the identity of the various oxides and acids formed and concentrate on the correct oxidation states only of chromium and manganese. We have to adopt the assumption that in general all the H_2O_2 is first consumed in producing a higher oxidation state of Cr or Mn, which being unstable decomposes to produce oxygen and lower oxidation states of the metals. The oxidation state of the dichromate may conveniently be taken as Cr_2O_6 . For four moles of H_2O_2 consumed (Fig. 1, A to F; Fig. 2, A & B) the steps may be written,

At smaller acid concentrations (Fig. 1, G; Fig. 2, C, D) a little more than four moles of H_2O_2 is required. This may hardly be explained on the basis that self-decomposition of the peroxide may set in under the changed conditions of the experiment. Alternatively, a small quantity of Cr_2O_6 may attain a still higher oxidation state, Cr_2O_{11} :

When an excess of $MnSO_4$ is present, only three moles of the peroxide are consumed. The colour changes accompanying the reduction indicate the following reactions:

FIG. 3

When a lesser quantity of acid is present (Fig. 3, F), the requirement of peroxide may be increased to 3.5 moles or more. Since the reaction,

appears to be unlikely, it is probable that a little of the Cr_2O_6 escapes reduction by MnSO_4 and reacts as if this salt were absent. The intermediate oxidation states discussed here are all unstable. Their identifications are therefore no simple matter. For the same reason it is hardly possible to understand these reactions on the basis of the corresponding redox potentials. We would show particular reluctance to the identification of Mn_2O_4 as manganese dioxide as this substance is a powerful catalyst for the decomposition of H_2O_2 in solution. As a first step towards confirmation of these mechanisms, it is necessary to measure the volume of oxygen evolved. This matter is receiving our attention.

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